

AIDAInnova

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

SMALL-SIZE PROTOTYPE OF A MPGD SINGLE PHOTON DETECTOR FOR COMPACT RICHs

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Abstract:

MicroPattern Gaseous Detectors (MPGD) for single photon detection has been developed within AIDA2020 (DELIVERABLE: D13.5) and fully validated by its successful application in the RICH counter of the COMPASS experiment at CERN SPS. Progress towards a compact RICH concept requires the use of novel photoconverters with the goal of major robustness and increased photoconversion rate to make the use of shorter radiators possible. A small size prototype of MPGD for single photon detection has been built and used to study a novel, alternative photoconverter. Encouraging results have been obtained. They pave the path towards further studies of the photoconverter properties towards applications in gaseous photodetectors.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

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Executive summary

The principle of MicroPattern Gaseous Detectors (MPGD) for single photon detection, developed within AIDA2020, is fully validated by its successful application in the RICH counter of the COMPASS experiment at the CERN SPS. Progress in the field requires novel more robust photoconverters with quantum efficiency similar or higher than CsI, used so far in gaseous detectors. A small-size prototype of MPGD-based photon detector has been built and used to validate a novel photoconverter by hydrogenized nanodiamond powder. The compatibility of the novel photoconverter with MPGD has been proven. The studies of its properties as photoconverter have been initiated with encouraging perspectives. Further work in the solid-state domain is needed to fully establish the novel photoconverter. The activity reported is the foundation for the next steps in the field.

1. INTRODUCTION

The most effective approach for high energy hadron identification is by Cherenkov imaging devices with a gas radiator. The ionizing particle path length in the gas must be long enough to ensure a sufficient number of detected photons to make particle identification possible and effective. The application of this approach is problematic in collider experiments generally and requires a compact layout.

Single photodetection for Cherenkov imaging application is by vacuum-based detectors, gaseous detectors and, more recently, by SiPMs. The rate of converted and detected Cherenkov photons is the highest with SiPMs, where the whole visible light spectrum is detected and peak Photon Detection Efficiency (PDE) can reach 70%. Vacuum-based detectors also cover the whole visible range with peak Quantum Efficiency (QE) up to 30-40%. So far, successful gaseous single photon detectors with solid-state photoconverters could only be equipped with CsI photoconverters, the less fragile among the photoconverters typically used in vacuum-based detectors. CsI converts VUV photons with a wavelength from 200 nm down. This feature combined with the typical wavelength cut of good quality fused silica windows (cut around 165 nm) limits the number of detected Cherenkov photons. CsI is chemically fragile and must always be manipulated and stored in controlled atmospheres: water vapour brakes its molecules. CsI in gaseous detectors is also subject to ageing effects due to the bombardment from the ions generated in the multiplication process in the gas. The QE is seriously degraded after an integrated charge of about 1 mC/cm² [1]. Nevertheless, gaseous photodetectors are attractive because of the low material budget, the capability to operate in magnetic field and because they offer the most effective solution concerning the cost of large-area applications. Therefore, the possibility to use gaseous single photon detectors in gas-radiator RICHes at colliders is related to the development of novel photoconverters aiming to overcome the present limitations: ageing and conversion rates.

The studies reported concern the compatibility of a novel photoconverter of increased robustness with respect to CsI and with the architecture and materials of a MPGD photodetector; they are complemented by some initial studies of the properties of the photoconverter itself in view of its future optimization.

2. PHOTOCONVERTER BY HYDRIGENIZED NADODIAMODS

Using innovative photoconverters in gaseous detectors is a strategic option. In fact, as recalled in the introduction, so far, the only solid-state photoconverter compatible with large-size, operative gaseous

detectors is CsI. In spite of remarkable successful applications (for instance the read-out sensors of the ALICE RICH [2], the COMPASS RICH [3] and the PHENIX HBD [4]), the use of CsI in gaseous detectors suffers of some intrinsic limitations: ageing, causing a severe decrease of the quantum efficiency after a collected charge of the order of some mC/cm^2 and long recovery time (about 1 day) after an occasional discharge in the detector. These limitations are related to the photon feedback from the multiplication region and the bombardment of the CsI photocathode film by positive ions generated in the multiplication process. They impose to operate the detector at low gain, reducing the efficiency of single photoelectron detection. Alternatively, great care is required to reduce the Ion BackFlow (IBF). Moreover, CsI is chemically fragile: if exposed, even for short time, to atmospheres with water vapour the molecule is broken and, therefore, the QE is lost. This feature imposes to assemble the photon detectors in clean, controlled atmospheres, making the overall detector construction tedious and complex. Therefore, the possibility of an alternative photocathode material adequate for gaseous detectors is strategic. The QE of photocathodes by nanodiamond (ND) particles rich in graphite have been measured in vacuum: when the photocathode is hydrogenized, a QE as high as 47% at 140 nm has been measured [5]; globally, the quantum efficiency is non negligible in the VUV domain, below 210 nm. High QE-values have been measured both performing the hydrogen plasma treatment in situ (after forming the photocathode film on the substrate) and hydrogenizing the ND powder before coating the substrate with the photoconverting layer. The latter option is of great interest for gaseous photocathodes: in fact, the hydrogen plasma treatment requires high temperature ($> 800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) which is not compatible with the components of gaseous detectors. When the ND powder is hydrogenated (H-ND) before the cathode coating, the spray procedure by an ultrasonic atomizer used to form the photocathode does not require temperatures exceeding 120°C [6]: this is compatible with gaseous detector components. Preliminary tests of mechanical attachment of the photocathode and ageing due to exposure to air indicate that this photocathode material is robust. A principle difficulty related to the photocathode material has to be considered in view of further studies: the ND powder provided by the producers is a cheap material not selected according to the graphite content, nor in grain-size; therefore several different samples have to be purchased and then the graphite-rich ones have to be selected by Raman spectroscopy; no exact reproducibility of the raw material from producers can be envisaged at present.

The considerations on quantum efficiency and robustness of H-ND based photocathodes are the main motivation for the R&D presented in this report, which developed following two main threads: on one side, the measurement of the H-ND properties (Section 4), including the measurement of QE in a gas mixtures to confirm the possible application in gaseous detectors; on the other hand, the coupling of the novel photocathode with the THGEM technology (Section 5).

3. SMALL-SIZE PROTOTYPE OF MPGD-BASED PHOTON DETECTORS

MicroPattern Gaseous Detectors (MPGD) for single photon detection have been developed within AIDA2020 (DELIVERABLE: D13.5) and fully validated by its successful application in the RICH counter of the COMPASS experiment at CERN SPS [7]. The small-size prototype for the studies reported in the following is based on this experience. Therefore, the detector architecture of the photodetectors for COMPASS RICH and their main performance parameters are shortly recalled.

The COMPASS RICH detector architecture is based on a hybrid MPGD combination (Fig. 1), consisting of two layers of THick GEMs (THGEM) followed by a resistive MicroMegas (MM) on a pad segmented anode. The first THGEM also acts as a reflective photocathode: its top face is coated with a CsI film. The feedback of photons generated in the multiplication process is suppressed by the presence of two THGEM layers with staggered holes, while the large majority of the ions from multiplication are trapped in the MM stage. The measured rate of IBF to the photocathode is at the 3% level. MPGD properties ensure signal development in about 100 ns. The high voltage is constantly adjusted to follow the environmental conditions, temperature and pressure, and the resulting gain stability is at the 5% level. No HV trip is observed during detector operation: in case of occasional discharges, only current sparks are observed, which temporarily affect the local performance. The restoration after a current spark is completed within 10s and the current spark rate is typically $<5/h/m^2$. These figures result in totally negligible dead-times related to sparks. The electronics noise, substantially uniform over the detector surface, is at the 900 electrons equivalent level (r.m.s). The space resolution is as expected for the $8 \times 8 \text{ mm}^2$ pads. The gain ranges between 13k and 14k, among the highest gain ever observed in MPGD in running experiments. The efficiency for single photoelectron detection is higher than 80%.

The small-size prototype [8] is based on the same architecture, with a single relevant modification: a single THGEM layer is used (Fig. 2). This modification is based on the following consideration: the two staggered THGEM layers largely contribute to the reduction of ion backflow rate, a key parameter in the experiment to prevent ageing over years of operation. This is not a requirement for the study of the novel photocathode, while a single THGEM configuration simplifies detector handling and THGEM replacement, two features that facilitate the R&D exercises that are needed to establish the new photoconverter. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the prototype detector components. All refinement and quality assessment protocols developed for the COMPASS RICH sensors have been applied, the most relevant being the THGEM polishing with pumice powder, the verification of its appropriate electrical stability (Fig. 5) and the measurement of the micromesh-anode distance in the MM (Fig. 6). The prototype has been characterized with ionizing particles using a ^{55}Fe source and with single photoelectrons from an UV laser source (255 nm pulsed laser head driven by a PDL 800-D controller, both from PicoQuant). Using the ionizing source, the single elements of the detector, namely the THGEM and the MM could be individually characterized, while a global characterization has been performed with the light source, by optimizing each single parameter (Figures 7 and 8). The prototype fully qualified for the photocathode studies.

Figure 1: Sketch of the architecture of the COMPASS RICH MPGD-based photodetectors: two THGEM layers are coupled to a resistive bulk MM. Image not to scale.

Figure 2: Sketch of the architecture of the small-size prototype: a THGEM layer is coupled to a resistive bulk MM. Image not to scale.

Figure 3: Back (left) and front (right) view of the anode plane. On the back face, the 470M Ω SMD resistors connected to each pad can be seen.

Figure 4: The two windows of the chamber are shown: the kapton one for studies with ^{55}Fe source (left) and the fused silica one for photon detection (centre). The drift plane (right) is compatible with both windows.

Figure 5: Setup for the measurement of THGEM breakdown voltage (Paschen test).

Figure 6: Optical measurement of the micromesh-anode distance: (left) the mesh is focused, (right) the anode pad surface is at the focal plane.

Figure 7: Gain as a function of the Micromegas voltage for three different pads.

Figure 8: Gain versus the electric field across the THGEM measured in different pads.

4. STUDY OF THE NOVEL PHOTOCONVERTER PROPERTIES

The standard procedure of hydrogenation of ND powder photocathodes is performed by using the MicroWave Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (MWPECVD) technique. For the treatment in microwave H_2 plasma, the ND powder is placed in a tungsten boat and, due to the microwave power, its temperature reaches values higher than 1100 °C. ND it is exposed to H_2 plasma for 1h. Therefore, the MWPECVD technique cannot be used to hydrogenate ND coated THGEMs since the dielectric material (fiberglass) would not sustain temperatures above 180 °C. The novel, alternative technique to overcome this limitation consists in a two-step procedure. First, the ND powder is hydrogenated as described above. Then, a solution is prepared with the hydrogenated powder and deionized water in one-to-one proportion; the solution is sonicated for one hour and sprayed on the desired substrate using a pressure atomizer in pulses of 100 ms, called shots, at about 3 Hz frequency. The substrates are kept at $\sim 150^\circ C$ and rotated by a magnetic stirrer. For our studies, we have coated with H-ND by the spray technique small size plates of Cu-coated fiberglass, in the following indicated as ‘coins’ and THGEMs. Coins are used to study the novel photoconverter properties. The spraying procedure has been used also for coating with non-hydrogenated ND powder for comparative studies.

The effective coating of the surface depends on the number of shots. A preliminary study was done to determine the optimal number of shots by measuring the quantum efficiency of substrates coated with a different number of shots. When the number of shots ≥ 100 , the QE has no appreciable variation (Fig. 9).

To study the robustness of H-ND based photocathodes, the QE was measured for different irradiation doses at the ASSET facility of the Gas Detector Development laboratory at CERN. The setup was formed by two main chambers, one used for QE measurements in vacuum, the other one for ion bombardment; the samples are moved from one chamber to the other by an automated manipulator under vacuum, therefore preventing exposure to air. For our studies, ions are generated by avalanche multiplication in gas: an X-ray source illuminates the gas volume, while a suitable electric field is established between the sample and a metallic grid fixed at 5 mm above the sample. Quantum efficiency is studied in the wavelength range 130-180 nm. The accumulated charge goes up to about 8 mC/cm². For comparison, a freshly CsI coated sample is tested under the same irradiation conditions. Results of the measurements are reported in Fig. 10. The QE of H-ND is reduced to $\sim 50\%$ for an integrated charge of about 5 mC, while the quantum efficiency of CsI, even initially higher, is reduced

to 50% for an integrated charge of about 0.5 mC. Resulting QEs are lower than those of H-ND for integrated charges of 1 mC. H-ND can tolerate 10 times more integrated charge by ion bombardment than CsI.

Figure 9: H-ND quantum efficiency versus the number of shots in the coating procedure.

Figure 10: Absolute quantum efficiency measurement of HND and of CsI versus the integrated charge.

The typical values of QE reported in literature are measured in vacuum. In gas the effective QE is reduced due to the interactions of the photoelectrons with the gas molecules and depends on the gas species and the electric field, which accelerates the photoelectrons and, therefore, the cross-sections of their interaction with the gas molecules. This had been studied for CsI and a variety of gasses and gas mixtures. We have repeated similar measurement for the H-ND photoconverter. For our studies, the UV photons are generated by a deuterium lamp and the wavelengths are selected by a monochromator. The currents are read out via a picoampere meter. The sample is contained in a

chamber where a gas mixture is flushed; the electric field is established by a grating of thin wires arranged between the sample and the chamber window. A calibrated photodiode by the National Institutes of Standards and Technology (NIST) makes absolute measurements possible. From the experience with COMPASS RICH, we know that using a CsI photoconverter the effective QE is maximized in methane or in methane-rich argon-methane mixtures. The results obtained with H-ND (Fig. 11) are in agreement with what already observed for CsI photoconverters, therefore confirming that the effective QE reduction in gas is related to the scattering of the photoelectrons with the gas molecules.

Figure 11: Photocurrent at wavelength of 160 nm versus the electric field. Different Ar-CH₄ gas mixtures are tested. In the insert the photocurrent versus the methane percentage at a wavelength of 162 nm is presented.

5. THGEMS AS SUBSTRATE OF THE NOVEL PHOTOCONVERTER

The studies presented in Sec. 4 suggest that H-ND photoconverter can be used in gaseous counters to detect photons in the UV range. We have explored its portability in the technology of the MPGD-based photon detectors used for the COMPASS RICH.

Thirty small size THGEMs (Fig. 12) were produced with the COMPASS standard characteristics. THGEMs are 400 μm thick, coated with a 35 μm thick Cu, a 5 μm layer of Ni and a 200 nm layer of Au on both sides; holes have no rim, thus no CU-uncoated ring around the holes, have 400 μm

diameter and are arranged in a triangular pattern with 800 μm pitch. The produced THGEMs underwent a post-production process following the standard COMPASS RICH protocol.

Figure 12: The produced THGEMs arranged in the oven for the drying procedure.

The THGEMs are tested in an Ar / CO₂ mixture of 70% / 30% with constant monitoring of temperature and pressure of the gas, to ensure the possibility to compare data taken at different environmental conditions. Pressure and temperature data are recorded at a 1 Hz rate during the characterization process for gain correction. THGEMs are characterized using a ⁵⁵Fe X-ray source. This characterization performed before coating, offers, for each individual sample, a set of reference data for comparison after the photoconverter film is deposited.

THGEMs are coated with different powders via the spraying technique. After the coating, THGEMs are stored in an oven at 120 °C for about 48h to remove the water that could have been trapped during the spraying of the nanodiamond solution. Then, the coated THGEMs are characterised. An important parameter that can be extracted from the characterization is the maximum voltage at which the THGEM can be safely and stably operated. The test is carried out to determine whether the coating affects the detector stability. Table 1 presents the maximum voltage for different THGEMs and different coating, clearly indicating that the THGEM electrical stability is not affected by the coating procedure.

Uncoated THGEM	ΔV_{max} [V]	Coating	ΔV_{max} [V]
TB XV	1325	H-ND BDD	1325
TB XVI	1375	ND E6	1400
TB XVII	1350	ND BDD	1325
TB XXIV	1375	ND D&T	1325

Table 1: Maximum voltage that can be applied to 4 THGEMs before (column 2) and after (column 4) coating for coating with different ND / H-ND powders.

The THGEM gain at 1250 V (with temperature and pressure corrections with respect to the reference environmental conditions) before and after coating are compared in Table 2. There is no evidence that the nanodiamond coating enhances or reduces the gain of the chamber.

Uncoated THGEM	Effective Gain	Coating	Effective Gain
TB XV	82	H-ND BDD	87
TB XVI	75	ND E6	63
TB XVII	84	ND BDD	69
TB XXIV	82	ND D&T	91

Table 2: Gain of 4 THGEMs before (column 2) and after (column 4) coating for coating with different ND / H-ND powders. Gain is measure at 1250 V applying temperature and pressure correction respect to reference environmental conditions.

A study of the gain versus the THGEM biasing voltage, presented in Fig. 13, shows that the exponential dependence of the gain versus the voltage is not modified by the nanodiamond coating.

Figure 13: Gain versus biasing voltage of the 4 THGEMs with different coating of Table 2.

Our studies support the evidence that THGEM electrical properties and their performance as electron multipliers are not affected by ND / H-ND coating.

6. CONCLUSION

While the principle of MPGD-based single photon detectors was already validated by its application in the COMPASS RICH, the introduction of novel photoconverters has been identified as the key step forward for the progress of gaseous single photon detectors. It is requested that the photoconverter candidates are more robust concerning chemical stability and radiation hardness and capable to overcome the QE of the only photoconverter used so in gaseous photodetectors, namely CsI.

Our studies have been dedicated to exploring a possible option, namely H-ND. The possibility to use this photoconverter has been open by the new approach of separating the hydrogenizing phase, which requires very high temperature, and the coating phase at moderate temperature.

Our studies have demonstrated that H-ND coating is fully compatible with MPGD-based photodetectors. This has been demonstrated using a small size prototype with the same architecture of the COMPASS RICH sensors. We have also performed an initial exploration of the photoconverter properties, in particular of its radiation hardness.

This work represents a good foundation for a next step of studies, namely those dedicated to maximising the QE of H-ND. This following effort would require a team where solid-state experts and particle physicists work together towards the goal. In view of further studies, a scientific article summarizing our effort is in preparation [9].

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